

Appendix A: Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) criterion

The selected criteria are aimed at assessing UEPMs with respect to their abilities to consider (C), identify (Id), integrate (Int), and scale up (S) renewable energy in cities; Table 1 classifies each criterion according to these categories. Table 1 also describes the scoring rubric and weighting for each criterion. The criteria, scoring rubrics, and weightings have been determined based on expert consultation. The assigned scores and weights are naturally subjective, but provide the reader with sufficient transparency to adjust values according to their needs and preferences.

Table 1: Assessment criteria descriptions, category grouping (G), scoring rubric (from 0 to 3) and weighting (W) (from 1 to 4)

ID	Criteria	Description	G ¹	Scoring rubric	W
1	Scalability	- Suitability for analysis on different scales; e.g., buildings, districts/neighborhoods, small to large city sizes - Suitability for analysis/design of both new city segments (i.e., greenfield approach) and existing systems (i.e., brownfield approach)	S	3: suitable for analysis at all scales, for green and brownfield analyses 2: aimed at a smaller range of scales (e.g., city-wide or single system only) or only for green or brownfield analysis 1: single scale/application focus 0 or N/A: not suitable for urban RET analysis	2
2	Time resolution	- Granularity of time resolution/time steps for modeling and its suitability for considering RETs - Flexibility/customization in defining time steps; is it possible to model different time resolutions (low to high)?	C	3: customizable resolution from sub-hourly to multi-yearly 2: smaller range of resolution options, down to at least an hourly scale 1: time step longer than one hour 0 or N/A: no time consideration	2
3	Time horizon	- Modeling time horizon into the future - Flexibility to define short or long-term analysis	S, C	3: flexible time horizon from one to many (i.e., at least 50) years 2: limited range (e.g., from medium to long-term or to less than 50 years) 1: short-term only (e.g., one year) 0 or N/A: no time consideration	3
4	RET modeling	- Ability to model a wide range of renewable energy technologies - Ability to specify sufficient technical detail (e.g., technology efficiency, availability, technology aging/degradation, curtailment, performance based on ambient or part-load conditions, multiple inputs/outputs, etc.)	C	3: all RETs can be modeled with a sufficient level of technical detailing 2: most RETs can be modeled or technical detailing is limited 1: small RET range or simple technical detailing 0 or N/A: no RET consideration	4
5	CET modeling	- Ability to model a wide range of conventional energy technologies - Ability to specify sufficient technical detail (e.g., technology efficiency, availability, ramping rates, technology aging/degradation, performance based on ambient or part-load conditions, multiple inputs/outputs, etc.)	Int	3: all CETs can be modeled with a sufficient level of technical detailing 2: most CETs can be modeled or technical detailing is limited 1: small CET range or simple technical detailing 0 or N/A: no CET consideration	3
6	Storage modeling	- Ability to model a wide range of energy storage technologies - Ability to specify sufficient technical detail (e.g., charging/discharging efficiency, standby losses, state-of-charge, depth-of-discharge, aging/degradation, temperature effects, etc.)	Int	3: all storage devices can be modeled with a sufficient level of technical detailing 2: most storages can be modeled or technical detailing is limited 1: small storage range or simple technical detailing 0 or N/A: no storage consideration	2
7	Network representation	- Ability to represent networks or network elements (e.g., electricity grid, district heating, natural gas grid, other transport/distribution networks) - Ability to represent network technical details (e.g., efficiency, losses, sizing, power flow, operational details such as voltage / pipeline pressure / pipeline temperature, etc.)	Int	3: adequate network representation and technical detailing for a broad range of network types 2: some network elements/types can be represented or technical details are limited 1: basic network aspects (e.g., imports/exports, copper plate models) or few network types can be represented 0 or N/A: no network representation	1
8	Sector and system integration	- Sectoral representation within a city - Modeling of system interactions (e.g., between sectors, between sectors and technologies, between city system boundaries and outside world through energy trade/imports/exports, modeling multi-area/region systems, etc.)	Int, S	3: all sectors and system interactions are well-represented 2: most sectors and system interactions are represented 1: significant sectoral aggregation and low resolution system interactions 0 or N/A: no sectoral representation or system integration	3

¹ Criterion categorization with respect to renewable energies: C - considering, Id - identifying, Int - integrating, S - scaling up, Ind - Indirect

9	Demand-side representation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Representation of end-use demand for different types of energy carriers (e.g., electricity, space heat, hot water, process heat, natural gas, etc.) - Demand technology representation (e.g., lighting, appliances, vehicles, etc.) 	Int	3: all end-use demands and/or demand techs can be represented 2: most end-use demands are represented 1: single demand focus 0 or N/A: no demand-side representation	2
10	Supply-side representation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Representation of different types of supply energy carriers (e.g., fuels and energy resources including renewables) - Representation of the energy supply mix of a city (e.g., electricity and fuel mix) 	C, Int	3: all supply energy carriers can be represented 2: most supply energy carriers are represented 1: single supply focus 0 or N/A no supply-side representation	2
11	Policy mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to model policy mechanisms important for renewables integration (e.g., carbon taxes, subsidies, carbon targets, time-of-use tariffs, real time tariffs, feed-in tariffs, etc.) 	Id, Int	3: wide range of policy mechanisms/targets can be modeled and evaluated 2: some policy mechanisms can be modeled 1: limited policy mechanisms can be modeled 0 or N/A: not suitable for policy evaluation	3
12	Emissions modeling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to calculate different emissions generated by the entire energy system (i.e., to identify low emission pathways with high renewable shares) - Ability to breakdown emissions by source 	Id	3: all emissions are calculated and sourced 2: several key emissions are calculated or emissions cannot be sourced 1: only one emission category is calculated / sourced 0 or N/A: no emissions are calculated	3
13	Scenario modeling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to model different scenarios, including climate scenarios and sustainability goals/targets (i.e., to explore pathways to promote RETs) 	Id	3: ability to model and compare a wide range of scenarios 2: a smaller range of scenario types can be evaluated 1: limited scenario design options, focused on snapshot scenarios 0 or N/A: tool not designed for scenario modeling/comparison	2
14	Cost representation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calculation of relevant costs, including all technology costs (e.g., capital costs, operation and maintenance, fuel, balancing, salvage, etc.) 	C, Id	3: all system costs are considered 2: most costs are considered 1: basic costs are considered 0 or N/A: no costs are considered	3
15	Sizing/operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model's ability to provide insights into capacity and operational/dispatch planning (including for RETs) 	Id, Int, S	3: both capacity and dispatch planning insights 2: either capacity or dispatch planning insights 1: basic capacity or dispatch planning insights 0 or N/A: tool not designed for capacity or dispatch planning	3
16	Spatial consideration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to represent spatial constraints and design parameters 	Int	3: detailed spatial specifications modeled (e.g., GIS) 2: indirect spatial representation (e.g., within and between regions) 1: basic, indirect spatial representation (e.g., constraints in single region only) 0 or N/A: no spatial representation	1
17	Tool licensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - License type and cost 	Ind ²	3: free to download for anyone and/or open source 2: free for certain users or low-cost commercial license (<=2000 USD/year) 1: high cost commercial license (>2000 USD/year) 0: tool not available	2
18	User friendliness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ease of use of tool; e.g., intuitive graphical user interface (GUI) interaction - Training time required - Skill set required (e.g., programming knowledge or other specialized training) - Available support (e.g., help desk, community forums, etc.) - Availability of supporting input parameter databases (e.g., technology or environmental database) 	Ind ³	3: well-developed GUI, technical support and/or supporting databases 2: basic GUI available, limited support, short training time/basic skills required 1: high technical skills/training time required, GUI is basic, poor or not available, no supporting input databases 0: tool not available or functioning	3
19	Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparency in terms of underlying assumptions, calculations, and methodology - Quality of available documentation 	Ind ³	3: open source code and supporting documentation 2: high quality documentation with most of the model structure explained 1: limited documentation and low transparency of model structure 0: no documentation on underlying model structure	2
20	Technical flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to adapt or customize tool to user needs (e.g., custom constraints, build new modules) - Ability to integrate/interface with other tools (e.g., Excel data, GIS data, CityGML, other modules, etc.) 	Ind ³	3: highly flexible tool in terms of customization, integration and development options 2: some technical flexibility in terms of customization and integration 1: limited technical flexibility 0: no technical flexibility, plug-and-play package	1

² Indirect - accessibility of tool for RET analysis

³ Indirect - usability of tool for RET analysis

Appendix B: UEPM details

Table 2: Tools under investigation – name, age, developer, license, databases and local-scale applications; abbreviations described in footnotes

Tool	Full name	Year est.	Developer/maintainer	License ⁴	Included Databases	Local-scale studies
Balmorel	-	2001	Hans Ravn	F, OS	-	[1], [2]
CURB	Climate Action for Urban Sustainability	2016	World Bank Group	F	city data	[3]–[5]
EnergyPLAN	-	1999	Aalborg University	F	default tech data	[6]–[13]
ENPEP-BALANCE	Energy and Power Evaluation Program	1999	Argonne National Laboratory	F (NGO, gov't, research)	-	[14]
eTransport	-	2001	SINTEF	F (academic)	-	[15] (19 studies)
GEMIS	Global Emissions Model for Integrated Systems	1989	International Institute for Sustainability Analysis and Strategy (IINAS)	F, OS	lifecycle database	[16]
HOMER	Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources	1992	National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)	F, C (\$1500/yr)	resource, load profile, component libraries	[17]–[37]
LEAP	Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning	1980	Stockholm Environment Institute	F (non-OECD)	technology and environmental database	[38]–[58]
MESSAGE	Model for Energy Supply Strategy Alternatives and their General Environmental Impact	1980s	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)	F (academic, IAEA members), F&OS (MESSAGEix)	global regional data	[59]–[63]
MODEST	Model for Optimization of Dynamic Energy Systems with Time dependent components and boundary conditions	1990s	Dag Henning	proprietary, not available for purchase	-	[64], [65] (several studies), [66]
OSeMOSYS	The Open Source Energy Modeling System	2010	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	F, OS	-	[67]–[72]
RETScreen	RETScreen Clean Energy Project Analysis Software	1996	Natural Resources Canada	F, C (\$800/yr)	city & tech library	[73] (130+ studies), [74]–[76]
SAM	System Advisor Model	2005	NREL & US Department of Energy	F, OS	location & tech library	[77] (10+ studies)
STREAM	Sustainable Technology Research and Energy Analysis Model	2004	Technical University of Denmark	F, OS	default tech data	[78]
TIMES/MARKAL	The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System	1980 (MARKAL), TIMES (2000)	International Energy Agency	C (front-end, up to \$20000/yr), OS (GAMs code)	-	[79]–[93]
TRACE	Tool for Rapid Assessment of City Energy	2008	Energy Sector Management Assistance Program (ESMAP), World Bank Group	F	-	[94] (70+ cities adopted tool)
TRNSYS	Transient Systems Simulation	1975	University of Wisconsin	C (~\$4000/yr), OS	tech library	[95]–[99]
WASP	Wien Automatic System Planning	1972	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)	F (IAEA members)	-	[100]–[102]

⁴ License: F – free, C – commercial, OS – open source

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